

The Automation Tax Coefficient

A theoretical approach on how to calculate the displacement of jobs based on the Automation Tax Coefficient.

Abstract

As machines and automated processes enter the workforce more pervasively than ever, it will become inevitable to measure the number of jobs displaced using an Automation Tax Coefficient (ATC).

Proposal

Calculating the ATC is a fundamental part of calculating the number of jobs and workers displaced by automation. Depending on the displacement coefficient, we can calculate the amount of taxation which we should impose on machines. In simple words, we can measure it by calculating the number of workers it displaces.

Example

Machinery should be taxed unequally and differently, based on how many jobs it displaces. If for example, an automated process in industry displaces (or does the job) of five people, it should pay a tax of five people.

If the wage of a worker displaced is (x) and the machinery displaces five people, then the machine should pay the amount of $(5x)$ as a tax. If a piece of a robotic arm does the job of four people it should pay $(4x)$ taxes. If an app does the job of 6 employees than it should pay the amount of $(6x)$ as an ATC. If a piece of machinery displaces the job of 3 supervisors and their wage is (y) , the ATC should be $(3y)$. And so on.

Conclusion

Based on the number of jobs and workers displaced, the Automation Tax Coefficient is a vital component in calculating the “amount” of jobs displaced by machinery and robots. Based on these assumptions, the ATC is applied differently to different automation processes.

“The more jobs a machine displaces, the more taxes it should pay”

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